

Opinion

NoPFAS moms (and dads) meet inside the European Parliament in Bruxelles.

Lives Upended: Mothers No PFAS

Mamme No PFAS

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PFAS (per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances) are the chemical compounds that half of Veneto (Northern Italy) found in their blood from drinking tap water at home and from consuming local food products.

PFAS are the perfect pollutant: a very large family of chemical substances (we are talking about over four thousand compounds) that are now found almost everywhere: dispersed in air, water and soil, in large or small quantities. Once ingested, they are deposited in our organs and tissues and remain there for years, we don't know how many. They have no color, they have no odor, and they have certainly made our lives easier thanks to their water-repellent properties. It's a shame that they simultaneously poison us and our environment for the rest of our lives, because they are practically indestructible.

We, contaminated by PFAS, are no different in any way from other people, except for the fact that we have a certain (variable) quantity of PFAS in our bodies, and for the fact that we are a population that is simultaneously sicker and more at risk of getting sick, compared to less exposed populations.

The story begins in 2006, with the European PERFORCE Project¹, coordinated by Stockholm University, to

monitor the presence of perfluorinated substances (PFAS) in the waters of the major European rivers, and in Italy the Po River appeared to have higher levels compared to other rivers in Europe (McLachlan *et al.*, 2007). In 2011, an agreement between the Italian Ministry of the Environment and Land and Water Protection (MATTM), the Water Research Institute (IRSA) and the Italian National Research Council (CNR) launched a study on the environmental risks from PFAS contamination in the Po basin and in other Italian river basins. In 2013 the Veneto Regional Agency for Environmental Protection (ARPAV) discovered that the main source of pollution was the chemical company Miteni S.p.A. of Trissino, in the province of Vicenza, but this information was not disclosed to the public. Between 2015 and 2016, the Veneto Region launched its first biomonitoring campaign to verify the presence of PFAS in blood, sampling just over 500 people. Letters inviting people to volunteer blood samples were sent out, and citizens begin to be concerned. Given the worrying results of the first sample collection, shortly thereafter a Health Surveillance Plan (Pitter *et al.*, 2020) was conducted on the entire population exposed to contamination in a vast area of three Venetian provinces, Vicenza, Verona and Padua, and which at the time involved approximately 350,000 people.

In 2017, following the results of the first blood tests² carried out on their children, some mothers began to look for information: they wanted to understand what was happening and, not finding sufficient answers and information from the relevant bodies, they became increasingly worried and began to form small action groups, initially in Montagnana (PD) and Lonigo (VI), with the aim of understanding the problem, understanding why information was not conveyed correctly to citizens, and above all to take action to have clean water in schools, and then in hospitals and homes.

Our lives changed suddenly and radically: we started studying the "PFAS topic", we collected documentation, we organized information evenings, we literally knocked on every door to expose the problem. We also changed our habits: now we use bottled water for drinking and cooking, even for making coffee; we stopped buying local food products and looked for products that came from supposedly uncontaminated areas; shopping became complicated, our children learned to bring water to school in a bottle, and we mothers have to scrutinize every slightest sign of discomfort that could indicate the presence or onset of a related disease.

The network of people mobilizing spread like wildfire, and because they are mostly women, hence the name Mamme No PFAS.

Word of mouth and the creation of small thematic working groups, always connected to each other, have led us to become a very numerous, spontaneous, environmental movement, joining other associations that deal with health and the environment, a network from Greenpeace to Legambiente, but also ISDE and CILSA, Medicina Democratica, PfasLand, and others.

We coordinate with each other mainly using WhatsApp and Telegram channels, and different groups follow various aspects of the problem: food contamination, criminal trials, proposed law on limits, studies and research that are published, remediation of the Miteni site (a company now bankrupt), meetings with ministers, contacts with journalists, photographic projects, website, Facebook page, and anything else needed to advance the cause.

Over the years we have achieved important results, including the closure of the Miteni company, the start of a criminal trial, the widening of the age limits of people included in the Health Surveillance Plan. Most importantly, we have spearheaded the construction (still underway) of new aqueducts to provide clean

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/508967>

² At the moment it is possible to carry out PFAS blood tests only if you are or were a resident in the red zone, and it is the Veneto Region that makes the call, via letter to interested parties. There is no medical prescription code for PFAS tests. Recently the possibility of analysis has also been extended to residents of the orange zone, but only on a voluntary basis and under a health cost sharing regime.

water to homes in the contaminated area, while activated carbon filters have been installed on the water intakes of the most contaminated municipalities (defined as the red zone). However, filters must be periodically replaced, with citizens bearing the burden of cost through their water bill. Contaminated filters are sent to Chemviron at Legnago for recycling or reactivation, but some doubts persist that PFAS are being dispersed into the atmosphere. Another ongoing problem, still with no solution, is the fate of private wells that are often used for irrigation.

We have become the subject of documentaries,

universities to conduct new scientific studies that aim to demonstrate the effects of PFAS on physical and psychological health. Furthermore, we participate in Citizen Science research projects. Currently, we are contributing to a study on male reproductive health promoted by the Association of Doctors for the Environment (I.S.D.E.) of Vicenza; to a study on foods conducted by prof. Annibale Biggeri, and another study by the University of Padua is about to start.

We are not alone! We founded the *Moms from North to South* movement, which now includes 46 Italian women's associations. Additionally, we are in contact

many other associations. Further information [here](#).

On December 13, Marcos A. Orellana, United Nations Special Rapporteur on the human rights implications of the environmentally sound management and disposal of hazardous substances and waste, held a press conference in Rome to conclude his visit to Italy and stated:

«I am seriously concerned about the extent of PFAS pollution – declared Orellana – The human dimension of the problem was illustrated to us by one of the mothers met during the visit: “Imagine what it means for a mother to realize that she has poisoned her children through breast milk?”.

and:

«For several decades the Miteni chemical company had been producing PFAS in Trissino (Vicenza) and releasing its waste without control, polluting surface and underground waters and the food chain, affecting the areas of Verona, Vicenza and Padua. While company officials appeared to be aware of the waste discharges and resulting pollution, they did not offer adequate protective measures to its workers, nor did they disclose information about the severity of the PFAS pollution.»³

After the visit of the UN commissioner, we prepared a series of observations for the Italian Senate Environment Committee. In addition to substantiating the request for zero limits, we presented numerous observations regarding transparency on the substances used by companies, the need to introduce obligations on producers and users (including the obligation to provide analytical standards to be able to identify the substances produced and used), to fill gaps in environmental authorizations and to protect people's health, starting from the most vulnerable categories such as minors.

«We ask the Government and Parliament to have the courage to adopt zero limits for the presence of all PFAS, not only in water intended for human consumption, but also in industrial waste: this is the only value that allows us to guarantee the right to live in a clean and uncontaminated environment. Italy, the scene of the largest contamination in Europe, which affected three provinces of the Veneto region, needs an urgent moratorium on PFAS, which not only eliminates their presence in waste water, but also introduces a production ban and use in all industrial sectors. Our country has the opportunity to make history and, with a truly ambitious measure, put the rights of all people before the profit of a few. The time has come to act urgently and without depreciating compromises.»

In the meantime, the trial continues against Miteni, or rather, against 15 individuals, including managers of the multinationals **Mitsubishi Corporation** and **International Chemical Investors Group** (I.C.I.G.) and the former manager of the Miteni company in Trissino. The alleged crimes range from poisoning of water intended for public consumption, to malicious disaster, to environmental pollution, to fraudulent bankruptcy. The two previous indictments were brought together in a single proceeding for crimes up to 2013 and for those from 2013 to 2018 and has resulted in a combined trial.

The hearings have so far followed one another at a rapid pace, with illustrious testimonies such as those of the American lawyer Robert Bilott, who alone faced

NoPFAS moms meet outside the European Parliament in Bruxelles

theatrical performances, conferences, degree theses and books. We have achieved these results through constant and peaceful dialogue with all institutions, at all levels, and through grassroots actions to raise public awareness on this issue. We met the heads of public and administrative offices, including ArpaV (Regional Environmental Protection Agency), Provincial, Regional and Local Health Authorities; the Ministry of the Environment, heads of the ASL, Coldiretti, Confagricoltura (farmers' unions and lobbies), up to the European Parliament and Pope Francis. We also have frequent contacts with the EEB, the European Environment Bureau based in Brussels.

These meetings serve to take stock of the situation and understand what actions are being implemented to mitigate contamination. During these discussions we present our point of view, our perception of the situation and our requests. We always leave written documentation.

But we don't limit ourselves to words. We have organized several mass demonstrations: the first on 8 October 2017 in Lonigo, saw the participation of 11,000 people. We protested in front of the Region and the Miteni plant, and we held a protest lasting five days and four nights, in front of the Vicenza Prosecutor's Office, with tents and gazebos, and with our families, including children.

We collaborate with research institutes and

with anti-PFAS groups in North Carolina (USA), France and Belgium. This solidarity network strengthens our voice and our determination to obtain laws that ban the production and use of PFAS.

In 2019, 150 of us became civil parties in the criminal trial to define responsibility for PFAS pollution in Veneto. Thanks to fundraising, we have funded important consultancies that will help demonstrate the damage caused by the accused.

For our activities and to disseminate information on PFAS we mainly use social media, Facebook, WhatsApp and Instagram. We organize thematic evenings and hold talks in schools to educate young people on this issue.

We are fighting for a future where clean water is a right for everyone, not just for women, or our families, but for every person who lives on this earth.

In December 2021 we received a visit from a UN commissioner for the violation of human rights, who contacted us because we sent a letter, written jointly by Mamma No PFAS Michela Piccoli, by Giuseppe Unghereso of Greenpeace, and by Alberto Peruffo of PfasLand, exposing our case of contamination. We accompanied him to the symbolic places of the Red Area of Veneto contaminated by PFAS, and he then spent an entire afternoon with us collecting the numerous testimonies of the No PFAS Mothers and

³ The statement can be found [here](#).

NoPFAS moms meet lawyer Robert Bilott

and won the case against the American company DuPont (responsible for a contamination similar to ours, albeit on a more modest scale, which occurred in the American state of Virginia, and depicted in the film **Bad Waters**); of Dr. Fletcher, Boston pathologist; and finally of Professor Philippe Grandjean, one of the world's leading experts on diseases related to PFAS substances.

Confident that we will obtain justice for our children and future generations, we will continue to organize events and actions against a culture that puts profit first at the expense of our health.

To follow us:

[Website](#) or [Facebook](#)

References

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Suggested readings

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Suggested internet sites

<https://chemtrust.org/news/pfas-pollution-scandals/>

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/508967>

<https://foreverpollution.eu/>

<https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/emerging-chemical-risks-in-europe>

<https://www.epa.gov/pfas/pfas-explained>

<https://www.epa.gov/pfas/pfas-strategic-roadmap-epas-commitments-action-2021-2024>

<https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/portal-perfluorinated-chemicals/aboutpfass/>

<https://perforce3-itn.eu/>

Il Giornale di Vicenza Martedì 28 novembre 2023

Processo

L'esperto danese in aula
«Pfas, pericolo per il futuro»

Key witness, Prof. Philippe Grandjean, testifies in Mitteni trial.